

Derivatives of Salicylic Acid. Part III.

3-Sulphosalicylic Acid.

BY NARHAR WAMAN HIRVE.

On sulphonating salicylic acid one would expect to obtain 3- and 5-sulphosalicylic acids; but the former has never been described. The 5-sulpho-acid was obtained by (a) Mendius (*Annalen*, 1857, 103, 45), by (b) Remsen (*Annalen*, 1875, 179, 187), and by (c) Hirsch (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 3239). Remsen suspected the presence of another isomer in the mother-liquor. The suspicion was dismissed by Hirsch.

I have prepared 3-sulphosalicylic acid by sulphonating 5-nitrosalicylic acid and 5-aminosalicylic acid and then removing the superfluous group ($-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{NH}_2$) in the usual way.

In order to avoid the suspicion that the sulphonic acid group may migrate during the removal of the superfluous group, a careful comparison was made of the 3-sulpho- and 5-sulpho-salicylic acids. The following table shows numerous points of difference between the properties and composition of the acids and their salts.

	3-Sulphosalicylic acid.	5-Sulphosalicylic acid.
Crystalline form	... Silky needles.	Rectangular plates.
Solubility in sulphuric acid.	Easily soluble in cold.	Difficultly soluble in cold and hot.
Solubility in water	... Easily soluble.	Less soluble than the isomer.
Composition	... $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{S}$, $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{S}$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{S}$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Melting point	... $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{S}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O})$, 162°	Not definite.
Acid potassium salt	.. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{SK}$; difficultly soluble.	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{SK}$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, easily soluble.
Barium salt	... $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_6\text{SBa}$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; difficultly soluble.	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_6\text{SBa}$, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ easily soluble.

Further, when the 3-sulpho-acid was nitrated, the original 3-sulpho-5-nitrosalicylic acid was obtained; on bromination, 3-sulpho-5-bromosalicylic acid different from 5-sulpho-3-bromosalicylic acid was obtained. As this 3-sulpho-5-bromo-acid had not been described before, it was prepared also from 3-sulpho-5-aminosalicylic acid and was also converted by hydrolysis into the known 5-bromosalicylic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5-Amino-3-sulphosalicylic Acid.

Method I.—5-Aminosalicylic acid (10 g.) was heated with fuming sulphuric acid (20% free SO_3 ; 20 c. c.) for about four hours. The sulpho-acid separated on cooling and the mother-liquor gave more of it on dilution with water. It is insoluble in alcohol, benzene and acetic acid. It is difficultly soluble in boiling water and crystallises as pale violet cubes with one molecule of water of crystallisation (yield, 15.5 g.). It decomposes at 353° . (Found: equivalent, 125.7; S, 13.90; N, 5.71; H_2O , 7.32. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_6\text{NS}$, H_2O requires equivalent, 125.5; S, 12.77; N, 5.57; H_2O , 7.19 per cent.). If instead of boiling the solid with water, boiling water is poured on the solid, it goes into solution much more easily and on concentration of the solution it crystallises in long white needles with three molecules of water of crystallisation. These needles when heated with water are converted into the cubes. (Found: equivalent, 143.60; S, 11.28; N, 5.02; H_2O , 19.04. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_6\text{NS}$, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires equivalent, 143.5; S, 11.14; N, 4.88; H_2O , 18.81 per cent.).

Method II.—5-Nitro-3-sulphosalicylic acid (10 g.) was dissolved in strong hydrochloric acid (40 c. c.) and iron * powder (in excess) was slowly added to it. Heat developed as the reaction proceeded and the 5-amino-3-sulphosalicylic acid separated on completion of the reaction. The solid was collected and crystallised from boiling water (yield, 8.5 g.).

The *neutral sodium salt* is easily soluble in water and crystallises from it in discoloured needles, with three molecules of water of crystallisation. (Found: Na, 14.14; H_2O , 16.15. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{NSNa}_2$, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Na, 13.90; H_2O , 16.31 per cent.).

The *neutral barium salt* is difficultly soluble in boiling water and separates as pale violet granules. (Found: Ba, 37.59. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{NSBa}$ requires Ba, 37.29 per cent.).

5-Diazo-3-sulphosalicylic Acid.—5-Amino-3-sulphosalicylic acid (5 g.) was finely powdered and suspended in dilute hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) and a solution of potassium nitrite (0.5 g.) was slowly added to it, keeping the temperature below 40° . The acid potassium salt of the diazosulphosalicylic acid separated. It was collected and

* Mandt (Ber., 1877, 10, 1701) used tin. I find that tin soon becomes inactive when the sulphonic acid has not been carefully purified.

converted into the barium salt from which the diazo-compound was liberated. It is easily soluble in water and alcohol. It crystallises from water in reddish-yellow prismatic needles which decompose at 166° on heating rapidly and at 216° on slow heating (yield, 4.5 g.). (Found: equivalent, 122.1; N, 11.55. $C_7H_4O_6N_2S$ requires equivalent; 123.2; N, 11.48 per cent.).

The *acid potassium salt*, obtained as above, was crystallised from warm water. It formed shining pale yellow needles decomposing violently at 210° . (Found: K, 12.82; H_2O , 5.87. $C_7H_3O_6N_2^+SK$, H_2O requires K, 12.99; H_2O , 5.97 per cent.).

The *acid sodium salt* was obtained on diazotising the amino-sulpho-acid. It is easily soluble in water and was precipitated from the solution by addition of alcohol. It crystallises in pale shining yellow plates with half a molecule of water of crystallisation. It decomposes violently at 205° . (Found: equivalent, 274.0; Na, 8.11; H_2O , 3.15. $C_7H_3O_6SNa$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$, requires equivalent, 275.2; Na, 8.37; H_2O , 3.27 per cent.).

The *neutral sodium salt* is easily soluble in water and crystallises from it in red needles. (Found: Na, 15.91. $C_7H_2O_6N_2SNa_2$ requires Na, 16.00 per cent.).

The *neutral barium salt* is difficultly soluble in hot water and separates as yellow granules. (Found: Ba, 34.05; H_2O , 5.15. $C_7H_2O_6N_2SBa$, H_2O requires Ba, 34.58; H_2O , 4.58 per cent.).

3-Sulphosalicylic Acid.—The acid potassium salt of the 3-sulphosalicylic acid separated on refluxing the acid potassium salt of the diazo compound with a mixture of alcohol and water for about four hours. The disappearance of the azo-colour on coupling with alkaline β -naphthol indicated the completion of the reaction. The recrystallised acid potassium salt was converted into the barium salt from which the free acid was liberated in the usual way. It is easily soluble in water from which it crystallises in long needles having no definite m.p. It loses three out of five molecules of water on keeping overnight in a desiccator. This product has m.p. 152.5° . (Air-dried product: Found: equivalent, 153.6; H_2O , 32.32; S, 10.31. $C_7H_6O_6S$, $5H_2O$ requires equivalent, 153.67; H_2O , 31.73; S, 10.40 per cent. Desiccated product: Found: equivalent, 127.2; H_2O , 14.3; S, 12.4. $C_7H_6O_6S$, $2H_2O$ requires equivalent, 127.07; H_2O , 14.19; S, 12.61 per cent.).

The *acid potassium salt* is difficultly soluble in boiling water from which it crystallises in tiny white needles. (Found: equivalent,

255.3; K, 15.12. $C_7H_5O_8SK$ requires equivalent, 255.5; K, 15.27 per cent.).

The *acid sodium salt* was prepared by a similar method to that for acid potassium salt. It is easily soluble in water and crystallises from it in needles. (Found: equivalent, 267.2; H_2O , 9.6; Na, 8.48. $C_7H_5O_8SNa$, $1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires equivalent, 267.1; H_2O , 10.11; Na, 8.61 per cent.).

The *neutral barium salt* is very difficultly soluble in boiling water from which it crystallises in tiny white lustrous needles. (Found: Ba, 36.39; H_2O , 6.89. $C_7H_4O_8SBa$, $1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires Ba, 36.11; H_2O , 7.10 per cent.).

5-Nitro-3-sulphosalicylic Acid.—The 5-nitro-3-sulphosalicylic acid obtained on nitration of 3-sulpho-salicylic acid ($C_7H_5O_8NS$, $2H_2O$) and its phenolic barium salt $(C_7H_3O_8NS)_2Ba$, $12H_2O$ had the properties and composition ascribed to them (cf. Meldrum and Hirve, preceding paper).

3-Sulpho-5-bromosalicylic Acid.

Method I.—The acid potassium salt of 3-sulphosalicylic acid (10 g.) was exactly neutralised with potassium hydroxide and bromine vapour (6 g.) mixed with air was then passed into it. The acid potassium salt of the sulpho-bromo-acid separated. It was collected and recrystallised and converted into the barium salt from which the acid was subsequently liberated. It is easily soluble in water and crystallises from it in long colourless silky needles, with four molecules of water of crystallisation; m. p. 98-100°. On keeping overnight in a desiccator it loses two molecules of water when it melts at 174°; yield, 12.5 g. (Air dried substance: Found: equivalent, 185.8; H_2O , 19.43; S, 8.61; Br, 21.49. $C_7H_5O_8BrS$, $4H_2O$ requires equivalent, 184.6; H_2O , 19.51; S, 8.69; Br, 21.66 per cent.). Desiccated substance: Found: equivalent, 166.8; H_2O , 10.62; S, 9.53; Br, 23.92. $C_7H_5O_8BrS$, $2H_2O$ requires equivalent, 166.5; H_2O , 10.81; S, 9.62; Br, 24.01 per cent.).

Method II.—3-Sulpho-5-diazo-acid-potassium-salicylate (3 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of hydrobromic acid (46 c. c. 18%) and water (20 c. c.), and cooled to room temperature. To this solution copper powder (5 g.) was added in small quantities, with shaking after each addition. A vigorous effervescence ensued. The reaction was completed by heating the mixture to boiling till the effervescence ceased. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate gave the acid

potassium salt of 3-sulpho-5-bromosalicylic acid: the acid when liberated was identical with that already described.

The acid potassium salt was recrystallised from water in needles. (Found: equivalent, 335.3; K, 11.49. $C_7H_4O_3BrS$ requires equivalent, 335.2; K, 11.65 per cent.).

5-Bromosalicylic acid was obtained by passing superheated steam through the solution of 3-sulpho-5-bromosalicylic acid for about four hours. It crystallises in silky white needles, m.p. 164°. (Hüber and Heinzerling, Z., 1871, 710 give 164°-165°; Lassar-Cohn and Schultze, Ber., 1905, 38, 3294 give 165°-166°). (Found: equivalent, 216.6. $C_7H_5O_3Br$ requires equivalent, 217.0).

WILSON COLLEGE AND

ROYAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY.

Received August 30, 1930.

